

Operation and control of a 1- Φ induction machine fed from a typical transformer-less photovoltaic (PV) cells

Suha Sabah Shyaa, Nihad Abdulkudhur Jasim, Yihia Hussein Takheal, Donya Nuhad Mahdy

Department of Electrical Power Engineering Techniques, Technical College Al-Musaib, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University, Najaf, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

The work given in this paper illustrates how an adjustable speed 1- Φ induction machine's auxiliary winding is driven. Trina Solar's TSM-250PA05.08 array type model, which is made up of 1 series and 8 parallel-connected photovoltaic (PV) modules, feeds a single induction machine. PV system with perturb and observe (P&O) technique for maximum power point tracking (MPPT) tracking. The induction motor has been controlled using the field-oriented control (FOC) controlling approach. The outcomes of the 1-induction motor simulation were closely related to the parameters of insolation change. The outcomes are taken into account for the system's reaction FOC, which had been demonstrated in electromagnetic torque T_e , main and auxiliary winding currents, and motor rotor speed.

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Corresponding Author:

Suha Sabah Shyaa

Technical College Al-Musaib, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University

Najaf 54003, Iraq

Email: suha.odah@atu.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

As pollution is the most dangerous enemy for the earth's healthy environment, renewable energy has been used widely to overcome this danger [1], [2]. The significance of renewable energy is their types, such as solar, wind, geothermal and water energy, in employing it for generating electrical power, especially in remote areas, as solar energy is an inexhaustible supply of energy that may be utilized using the photovoltaic (PV) system [3], [4].

Solar energy can be utilized for different implementations such as water pumping, battery charging and grid network feeding [5]. The solar PV-based 1- Φ induction motor is widely utilized. Recently, the 1- Φ induction motor as one of the famous AC motors used in many applications such as refrigerators, vacuum cleaners and agricultural equipment [1]–[3]. The numerous uses of AC motors are mainly related to their simplicity in structure, outstanding reliability and low repair cost that is relatively less expensive [6], [7].

To harvest the maximum power from solar PV, the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) system using perturb and observe algorithm is influential and efficient [8], [9]. This paper studies the operation and control of a 1- Φ induction motor fed from typical transformer-less photovoltaic (PV) cells. The speed of a 1- Φ induction motor controlled by field-oriented control field-oriented control (FOC) technique.

2. THE PROPOSED SYSTEM DESIGN

The proposed system uses an h-bridge solar converter, as stated in Figure 1. The electrical energy is generated through PV cells. It does this by converting solar energy into electrical energy. The h-bridge

converter the PV array's output voltage to preserve the DC link voltage, as stated in Figure 2. Drive of 1- Φ induction motor (the induction motor is driven by a rectifier, a braking chopper and an insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) inverter) is applied to aid variable speed performance in achieving maximum power point tracking (MPPT). A single-phase induction motor (SPIM) drive is designed for a 1/4 HP, at voltage 110 V and frequency 60 Hz single phase AC motor with its main and auxiliary windings operation mode. A one-phase h-bridge converter feeds the SPIM. The converter utilizes the pulse width modulation (PWM)-control strategy. The speed control loop produces flux and torque references for the block controller by applying a proportional integral (PI) controller. Field-oriented control (FOC) controlling has been employed to control the induction motor.

Figure 1. The proposed system designs

Figure 2. Full h-bridge schematic

2.1. PV array design characteristics

A PV cell's properties can be characterized as an electrical equivalent circuit, as illustrated in Figure 3. The most commonly used semiconductor dependent on building solar panels is silicon due to its high ability to control conductivity [10], [11]. Electricity is generated directly by converting solar energy to electricity from solar cells. These cells are formed in modules [6], [10]. Several PV modules, called an array, are often utilized to meet different energy demands [10], [12]. In this paper, Trina Solar TSM-250PA05.08 array model implements a PV array constructed from parallel-connected and series-connected PV modules. On the PV array block, two inputs allow for the supply of varying sun irradiance and temperature data, where (input I_r in W/m^2) and (input T in degrees Celsius) respectively. The PV array consists of one string of eight Trina Solar TSM-250PA05.08 modules connected in series. At 25° and an irradiance of $1000 W/m^2$, the string can produce 3486 watt. To simulate parasitic capacitance between photovoltaic modules and ground, tiny capacitors (two capacitors linked at PV array terminals) are used.

A circuit stated in Figure 3 can be represented by the volt-ampere equation of a PV system stated by (1) [13], [14].

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D * \left(\frac{e(V+I*R_s)}{N * k_B * \frac{T}{q}} - 1 \right) - \frac{(V+I*R_s)}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

$$I_{ph} = I_{ph0} * \frac{I_r}{I_{r0}}$$

Where I_{ph} : solar-induced current, I_r : irradiance falling on the cell (light intensity), in W/m^2 , I_{ph0} : solar-generated current measured for irradiance I_{r0} , I_D : reverse diode's saturation current, R_s and R_{sh} : series and shunt resistance respectively in ohm, k_B : Boltzmann constant, T : the value of the device simulation temperature parameter, q : an electron's elementary charge, N : ideality factor, and V = solar cell ports' voltage. PV array parameters are illustrated in Table 1.

Figure 3. single PV cell

Table 1. PV array parameters

Parameter	Single module	Complete array module
Maximum power at MPP	249.86	3486
Voltage at MPP	31	434
Current at MPP	8.06	8.06
V_{oc} (V)	37.6	526.4
$I_{s,c}$ (A)	8.55	8.55
Light-generated current I_L (A)	-	8.5795
Shunt-connected resistance R_{sh} (Ω)	301.8149	301.8149
Series -connected resistance R_s (Ω)	0.247	1.976
No. of series modules	-	8
No. of parallel modules	-	1

2.2. Perturb and observe (P&O) technique of PV system

MPP tracker utilization in the PV array is to track the MPP at any alternative changes in irradiation and temperature at all times [15]. The corresponding flowchart for executing perturb and observe (P&O) technique is illustrated in Figure 4 [13], [16]. The P&O method periodically raises or lowers the panel voltage while contrasting the PV output power with that of the previous cycle. If the perturbation causes the module's power to increase or decrease, the subsequent perturbation occurs in the opposite direction. The size of the step and the interval between algorithm repetitions are the two factors for this strategy. As a result, the two variables opt for a trade-off for quicker tracking with greater accuracy [15], [17].

Figure 4. P&O method flow chart

2.3. 1-Φ induction motor

1-Φ induction motor is an asynchronous AC motor formed from a stator and rotor, representing the fixed and moveable parts in the motor, respectively. In the 1-Φ induction motor, AC voltage is utilized by the stator, which induces an electromagnetic field. Additionally, the induced field induces a current in the rotor, which causes the rotor to revolve as a result of the creation of a second field that attempts to synchronize with the stator field [18], [19]. The 1-Φ induction motor schematic is illustrated in Figure 5 [20], [21]. The induction motor has the ratings stated in Table 2.

Figure 5. Equivalent circuit of unsymmetrical 1-Φ induction motor (stationary reference frame)

Table 2. Parameter of 1-Φ induction motor

Parameter	Value
Type of machine	Main and auxiliary winding
Rating	¼ hp
Voltage	110 volts
Frequency	60 Hz
Main winding resistance and inductance (stator)	2.02 Ω and 7.4 mH
Auxiliary winding resistance and inductance(stator)	7.14 Ω and 8.5 mH
Main winding resistance and inductance (rotor)	4.12 Ω and 5.6 mH
Initial speed (% synchronous speed)	0%

1-Φ induction motor drive included a 1-Φ induction motor, breaking chopper, inverter and rectifier. The gating pulses of the inverter are generated from the FOC controller, which its schematic has illustrated in Figure 6. Field-oriented control (FOC) is sophisticated control technology that tracks the speed of induction machine. FOC has been dependent on the requirements of high-performance speed and torque control responses to face the variation in online parameters. Utilizing of PI-controller in FOC causes overshoot and undershooting during the presence of load disturbance. For sinusoidally distributed stator windings, flux and torque are generated in alpha-beta frame [22]–[24]. A rotor flux position θ_s is the major part of FOC, that is determined as (2) [22].

$$\theta_s = \int \omega_s dt = \int \left(p \cdot \omega_m + \frac{i_q}{T_{id}} \right) dt \tag{2}$$

Where p =machine pole pairs. The alpha-beta components are converted to the direct-quadrature ones by the rotational transformation [25].

$$[D] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_s & \sin \theta_s \\ \sin \theta_s & \cos \theta_s \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

$$[i_d \ i_q]^T = [D][i_\alpha \ i_\beta]^T \tag{4}$$

In FOC, 1-Φ induction motor under PI vector control has the following dynamic equations [22].

$$\frac{d}{dt} i_{sd} = -\frac{1}{\sigma\tau_s} i_{sd} + \omega_s i_{sq} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s \tau_r} \varphi_r + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} v_{sd} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \varphi_r = -\frac{1}{\tau_r} \varphi_r + \frac{(1-\sigma)L_s}{\tau_r} i_{sd} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} i_{sq} = -\frac{1}{\sigma\tau_s} i_{sq} - \omega_s i_{sd} + \frac{P}{\sigma L_s} \omega_r \varphi_r + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} v_{sq} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \omega_m = \frac{P}{J} \varphi_r i_{qs} - \frac{1}{J} T_L \quad (8)$$

Where φ_r is the direct-axis rotor flux linkage, ω_s is synchronous angular speed, $\tau_s' = L_s / R_{seq}$, $\sigma = 1 - M^2 / L_s L_R$, $R_{seq} = M^2 / L_s^2$ and $\tau_r = L_r / R_r$ where, τ_r is the rotor time constant.

Figure 6. Diagram of FOC for 1- Φ induction motor

3. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The MATLAB program has evaluated the performance and characteristics of 1- Φ induction motor under several PV array conditions. The results have been taken according to the light intensity variation for three different temperature degrees. The results are taken under the response of utilization of FOC for the drive system by illustrating the motor's electromagnetic torque T_e and speed.

3.1. Simulation result of PV array

The V-I and V-P characteristics of Trina Solar TSM-250PA05.08 array type are demonstrated in Figures 7 and 8 respectively, for three levels. Both features are illustrated for the array at 1000 W/m² as demonstrated in Figures 7(a) and 8(a) respectively, and for 25° with specified irradiation as demonstrated in Figures 7(b) and 8(b) respectively. The V-I, V-P characteristics of the PV array and absorbed irradiance by the PV array in (w/m²), mean DC voltage in (v) and mean power in (w) generated by the PV array, are demonstrated in Figures 7, 8, and 9 respectively.

Figure 7. V-I characteristics of Trina Solar TSM-250PA05.08 array type: (a) array @ 1000 W/m² and specified irradiation; and (b) array @ 25° and specified irradiation

Figure 8. V-P characteristics of TSM-250PA05.08 array type: (a) array @1000 W/m² and specified irradiation; and (b) array @25° and specified irradiation

Figure 9. Absorbed irradiance by the PV array in (w/m²), mean DC voltage in (v) and mean power in (w) generated by PV array

3.2. Simulation result of 1-Φ induction motor

The results of 1-Φ induction motor simulated closely related to insolation change characteristics. The results are considered for the system's response FOC, which had been illustrated in electromagnetic torque T_e , main and auxiliary winding currents and rotor speed of the motor. Figure 10(a) illustrates the rotor speed of the 1-Φ induction motor, tracking its reference value optimally. Figure 10(b) illustrates the main and auxiliary winding currents. Figure 10(c) illustrates the T_e with a high settling time of 2 seconds.

Figure 10. 1-Φ induction motor simulation results (a) rotor speed, (b) main and auxiliary winding currents, and (c) electromagnetic torque T_e

4. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a 1- Φ induction motor that utilizes FOC fed from a Trina Solar TSM-250PA05.08 array type. The P&O technique had been depended on to track MPP in the PV array. The results show the behavior of the 1- Φ induction motor under step input change with a good response for rotor speed, Te and main and auxiliary winding currents. examines the operation and control of a one-induction motor that is powered by standard photovoltaic (PV) cells without a transformer. The field-oriented control FOC technique used to control the speed of a 1- Φ induction motor.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Suha Sabah Shyaa is a lecturer in Technical College Al-Musaib, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University(atu), Najaf, Iraq. She received the B.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University in 2005 and the M.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq, in 2020. Her research interests include the field of power electronics, renewable energy, motor drives, and flexible alternating current transmission. She can be contacted at email: suha.odah@atu.edu.iq.

Nihad Abdulkhudhur Jasim is a lecturer in Technical College Al-Musaib, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University(atu), Najaf, Iraq. He received the B.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from North Technical University in 2001 and the M.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq, in 2020. His research interests include the field of industrial informatics, power electronics, renewable energy, and Fact. He can be contacted at email: nihad.hammoud@atu.edu.iq.

Yihia Hussein Takheal is a lecturer in Technical College Al-Musaib, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University(atu), Najaf, Iraq. He received the B.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University in 2007 and the M.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from kazan notional research technical university, Kazan, Russia, in 2020. His research interests include the field of electrical power circuit design, renewable energy, and motor drives. He can be contacted at email: yihiahussein@gmail.com.

Donya Nuhad Mahdy is a lecturer in Technical College Al-Musaib, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University(atu), Najaf, Iraq. She received the B.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University in 2015 and the M.Eng. degree in electrical power engineering from Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq, in 2020. Her research interests include the field of power electronics, machine and genetic algorithm. She can be contacted at email: donya.saleh@atu.edu.iq.